

Meteorological Stations

Monitoring the world around us since 1864

MUNRO

R W Munro Limited

Monitoring the World Around us Since 1864

The Founder Robert William Munro, F.R.Met.Soc. 1839-1912

Established in 1864, R W Munro has become synonymous with meteorological and hydrological equipment sales and service. Since production of the first Dines Pressure Tube Anemometer in 1892, R W Munro has achieved a reputation for excellence in providing instruments and systems of the highest quality to measure, monitor and record environmental phenomena. Today, Munro products extend right across the technological spectrum. Combining the traditional reliability of Munro craftsmanship with the benefits of the latest electronics enables Munro to supply standard and specialist equipment to meteorological offices, water authorities and government departments world-wide.

Meteorological Stations

CONTENTS

	Page
Introduction	2
Wind Direction and Run of Wind	3
Temperature and Humidity	4
Wind Vane and Anemometer	4
Thermometers, dry-bulb and wet-bulb	4
Thermometers, maximum and minimum	5
Thermograph, Hygrograph and Hygrometers	6
Thermometer Screens	7/8
Earth Thermometers	9
Rainfall	9
Rain Gauges	10
Evaporation	10
Evaporimeter	11
Solar Radiation	11
Campbell-Stokes Sunshine Recorder	12
Barometric Pressure	12
Barometer and Barograph	

Note: Automatic Weather Stations, for installation where regular manual recording is not possible, are described in a separate Munro catalogue.

Meteorological Stations

Regular monitoring of temperature, humidity, rainfall, wind patterns and other environmental conditions, is required not only in synoptic and climatological stations for general weather forecasting but also for the successful operation of projects and activities in many parts of the world. For example, accurate data on local conditions is needed in irrigation control, in agriculture and forestry, in the chemical and other industries, in the leisure and tourist industries, environmental health and safety and other specific areas.

The form and content of the data required will naturally vary according to the nature of the activity involved and the geographic location. Versatility in the range and application of meteorological equipment available is important, so that complete weather stations can be planned to suit individual circumstances. Munro have many years of experience in the manufacture and supply of all instruments and accessories necessary for equipping such installations, with equipment built to British Meteorological Office specifications wherever relevant.

Stevenson Screen in a typical Munro Meteorological Station

Synoptic and climatological stations have to be established on level ground, well away from trees, buildings or other obstructions and are enclosed by open fencing to exclude unauthorised persons. The data required will depend on individual station needs but will involve measurements of, at least, several of the following environmental phenomena for which Munro can supply all necessary instruments. None of the equipment detailed in this catalogue requires an electricity supply.

Wind Direction & Run of Wind

The Wind Vane with its four direction arms provides accurate visual indication of wind direction.
The Cup Counter Anemometer gives direct indication of run of wind on a mechanical counter.
Both types of equipment are made to a British Meteorological Office specification.

Wind Vane, B.M.O. Pattern MK2B IM140

This instrument for indication of wind direction, satisfies all requirements for ensuring high accuracy. For a given change of wind direction, it will rotate with the minimum of friction and it is balanced to avoid bias towards any particular direction. The instrument consists of a horizontal arm, with a rectangular flat fin at one end and a counterweight at the other, mounted on a vertical spindle which can rotate freely in a journal ball bearing. The tubular support for the bearing incorporates a ring carrying the four direction arms and this is locked in position once correctly orientated.

Munro Cup Counter Anemometer IM119

This robust Anemometer is used at many agrometeorological stations in hot climates to indicate the run of wind at 2m above ground level and for estimating potential evapotranspiration. The three conical cups rotate the spindle at a speed proportional to linear wind speed and the motion is transmitted, via a worm gear, to a six-digit mechanical counter which indicates in mph, knots or km/hr. Average run of wind over any chosen period of time can be calculated by noting counter readings at the beginning and end of the cycle. Materials of construction for the equipment are chosen for long life, with freedom from corrosion and minimal maintenance.

Cup Counter Anemometer IM119A

This version has the counter display angled downwards, so that the figures can easily be read from ground level.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference IM140		Reference IM119 / IM119A	
Range	0° to 360° & cardinal points	Range	0 to 9999.99
Dimensions		Scale	knots or mph or km/hr
Height	449 mm	Resolution	0.01
Axis to fin tip	505 mm	Start threshold	3 knots
Axis to balance weight	177 mm	Dimensions:-	
Weight	4.5 kg	Height	270 mm
Fixing details	1½" BSP internal	Axis to outer cup edge	228 mm
Operating temperature	-40°C to +100°C	Cup diameter	127 mm
		Weight	3.4 kg
		Fixing details	½" BSP internal
		Operating temperature	-40°C to +100°C

R W Munro Ltd. reserve the right to alter specifications of equipment at any time, in the interests of improving quality and performance

Temperature and Humidity

Regular observation of dry-bulb and wet-bulb temperatures provides data from which vapour pressure, relative humidity and dew point can be calculated. Extreme screen temperatures (maximum and minimum) together with grass minimum and earth temperatures at various depths, are also essential readings for forecasting and many agricultural applications.

Ordinary Thermometers

Normally used in pairs to form a wet-and-dry bulb hygrometer, the ordinary mercury filled thermometer is usually mounted vertically within a thermometer screen. The bulb of one has a muslin cover kept wet by distilled water drawn from a reservoir. Ambient air temperature is provided by the dry-bulb. Relative humidity is calculated from the temperatures displayed by both thermometers.

Maximum & Minimum Thermometers

Usually mounted in a thermometer screen with a 2° incline to the horizontal, the mercury filled maximum and ethanol spirit filled minimum thermometers indicate the extremes of ambient air temperature experienced since the instruments were last reset. In operation, the Minimum Thermometer utilises a small black glass index which is drawn along the bore by the contracting liquid. The index remains stationary at the extreme position, until the thermometer is reset. A constriction to the bore of the Maximum Thermometer, between the bulb and scale, enables the mercury to expand as the temperature increases, but prevents the mercury receding as the temperature falls. The mercury column will remain at the extreme position until the thermometer is reset.

Ordinary Thermometers - for Wet-and-Dry bulb B855/B856

Maximum and Minimum Thermometers B843/B844 and B849/B850

These Sheathed Pattern Thermometers are manufactured in accordance with the requirements of the British Meteorological Office and to British Standard 692. The thermometer stem, subdivided every 0.5° for accuracy and figured at 5° intervals, is fused to the outer glass sheath to form a permanent seal so that no condensation can occur. A rubber ring, placed between the stem and sheath, supports the far end of the stem.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	range	accuracy	division	dimensions
B843	-10 to +65°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 14 mm
B844	-20 to +55°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 14 mm
B849	-25 to +50°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 14 mm
B850	-35 to +40°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 14 mm
B855	-20 to +55°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 14 mm
B856	-30 to +45°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	330 x 14 mm

R W Munro Ltd. reserve the right to alter specifications of equipment at any time, in the interests of improving quality and performance

Autographic Instruments

At full synoptic, agrometeorological, auxiliary and climatological stations, a Thermograph and a Hygrograph are placed within a large thermometer screen to monitor continuously air temperature and the relative humidity of the local environment. Readings are recorded on a scaled rectangular chart fitted round a rotating clock drum.

Thermograph B814

Hygrograph B815

Thermograph B814

Supported on a sturdy cast alloy base, the hinged cover is perforated on the top and three sides to allow free airflow around the temperature sensitive element. The temperature element is a bimetallic coil, whose curvature changes are magnified and transmitted to the recording pen. Also mounted on the base, the mechanical clock will rotate the recording drum either daily (D) or weekly (W), depending on choice of clock. As standard this model is fitted with a disposable cartridge pen, black in colour, which will allow many months of recording before replacement is necessary. Alternatively, a fibre nib, wetted with black ink, is also available. A wide choice of operating ranges allows this instrument to be configured to suit most applications.

Hygrograph B815

Presented in a similar case to the thermograph, this instrument records the relative humidity of the air. Humidity readings, normally expressed as a percentage, are obtained from the alteration in length of a human-hair element, which is then magnified and transmitted to a recording pen. Mounted on the sturdy cast alloy base, the mechanical clock will rotate the recording drum either daily (D) or weekly (W), depending on choice of clock. A disposable cartridge pen, green in colour, is fitted as standard and will allow many months of recording before replacement is necessary. Alternatively a fibre nib, wetted with green ink, is also available.

Mason's Pattern Hygrometer B840A

Mounted within a protective copper case, two mercury filled thermometers are positioned over a printed scale plate. This is divided every 1° and scaled at 5° intervals to allow calculation of relative humidity to an accuracy of 2%. A fabric sleeve, with one end immersed in a water filled plastic reservoir, surrounds one thermometer to produce a wet-bulb reading. The other thermometer indicates air temperature. Supplied with spare fabric sleeve and hygrometric tables, for the computations of relative humidity.

Mason's Pattern Hygrometer B840A

Kew Pattern Hygrometer B879 & B880

Manufactured to a British Meteorological Office design, this Hygrometer is normally located within a thermometer screen, but is easily accommodated elsewhere, since it is provided with a substantial mounting board. Two mercury filled thermometers, with their stems subdivided every 0.5° and figured at 5° intervals, are mounted onto laminated plastic scale plates. In turn, these scale plates are fitted to a marine plywood back board. Water drawn up from a glass reservoir by a cotton wick, provides moisture to a circle of muslin surrounding one thermometer bulb to produce a wet-bulb reading. The second thermometer will indicate air temperature. Supported by a metal strap attached to the back board, the water reservoir has a cover to prevent the ingress of contaminants.

Kew Pattern Hygrometer B880

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	range	accuracy	weight	dimensions mm
B814/1	0 to +50°C	±0.5°C	2.5 kg	190 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)
B814/2	0 to +60°C	±0.5°C	2.5 kg	190 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)
B814/3	-10 to +40°C	±0.5°C	2.5 kg	190 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)
B814/4	-20 to +40°C	±0.5°C	2.5 kg	190 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)
B815	0 - 100% RH	±5% RH	2.5 kg	220 (H) x 260 (W) x 130 (D)
<i>Suffix D for daily clock - W for weekly clock</i>				
B840A	-5 to + 50°C	±2% RH	250 g	290 (H) x 85 (W) x 35 (D)
B879	-20 to + 55°C	±2% RH	800 g	380 (H) x 140 (W) x 50 (D)
B880	-30 to + 45°C	±2% RH	800 g	380 (H) x 140 (W) x 50 (D)

R W Munro Ltd. reserve the right to alter specifications of equipment at any time, in the interests of improving quality and performance

Thermometer Screens

To allow a true comparison between temperatures, taken within the same site or at differing geographical locations, thermometers must be exposed in as near standard conditions as possible. Accordingly, those thermometers employed to determine air temperature, extremes of air temperature and humidity are located in a thermometer screen of an approved design. The screen protects the thermometers from the effects of direct radiation and precipitation, whilst allowing the free movement of air. Finished in white gloss paint, the screen is usually supported by means of a rigid iron stand, the base of which is set firmly in the ground. To comply with Meteorological Office requirements, the stand must elevate the screen so that the bulbs of the vertically mounted wet-and-dry bulb thermometers are 1.25 metres above the ground.

Stevenson Screen B835

Manufactured to a British Meteorological Office design, this screen is constructed from seasoned timber and finished with three coats of top quality white gloss paint, to reflect radiation. The front, back and side panels are double-louvered with the outer layer sloping down and outward. The front panel has two brass hinges at the base to form a door. When open, this is retained in the horizontal position by two chains. It can be padlocked when closed. The roof is double layered, with an air space between inner and outer components. The floor consists of three partially overlapping boards. Internal supports are arranged to accommodate either mahogany frame or plastic scale pattern thermometers.

Self Assembly Screen B836

The fully machined component parts will assemble to form a screen identical to the ready-made version B835, with all screws, panel pins, hinges, chains and a hasp being provided. The only additional materials required are glue, paint and a padlock. Detailed and illustrated instructions are provided.

Large Thermometer Screen B838

Designed to house two autographic instruments, a Thermograph and Hair Hygrograph, as well as Sheathed Pattern Thermometers, this screen is constructed from seasoned timber to a British Meteorological Office design. The four vertical panels are double-louvered and the floor consists of over-lapping boards. The front panel has two bottom mounted brass hinges to form a door. When open, this is retained in the horizontal position by two chains. A hasp and staple are fitted, so the door can be padlocked when closed. The resin-bonded marine plywood roof, double layered with an air space between inner and outer components, provides excellent weatherproofing. The complete screen is further protected by three coats of top-quality white paint.

Screen Stands for B837 & B839

The iron stand, which can be set in the ground, forms a rigid support for elevating a screen to the recommended height. Finished in black enamel, stands are available to suit the Stevenson screen or large thermometer screen.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	Int. dims. mm	Ext. dims. mm	Weight
B835	405 (H) x 445 (W) x 240 (D)	540 (H) x 580 (W) x 420 (D)	14 kg
B836	405 (H) x 445 (W) x 240 (D)	540 (H) x 580 (W) x 420 (D)	14 kg
B837 iron stand		1280 (H) x 480 (W) x 300 (D)	23 kg
B838	420 (H) x 990 (W) x 292 (D)	585 (H) x 1220 (W) x 495 (D)	39 kg
B839 iron stand		1380 (H) x 1240 (W) x 510 (D)	36 kg

R W Munro Ltd. reserve the right to alter specifications of equipment at any time, in the interests of improving quality and performance

Earth Thermometers

Additional thermometers are required for exposure outside the screen, usually on or near to the surface and at specified depths below the earth's surface. Three different types of Munro earth thermometers are available to meet requirements in many countries. All indicate temperature by the expansion of a mercury column and offer comparable standards of accuracy.

Symons Pattern B859

Manufactured to the requirements of the British Meteorological Office, a solid stem mercury filled thermometer is suspended within a transparent sheath made of stout glass tubing. Subdivided every 0.5° for accuracy and figured at 5° intervals, the scale is easily read through the outer glass sheath. The bulb of the thermometer is embedded in a micro-crystalline wax, so it will not be affected by changes in temperature when drawn to the surface to take a reading. Two rubber rings round the sheath, protect the glass during insertion and withdrawal. In conjunction with an earth tube, this thermometer can be used to measure earth temperature at depths of up to 3m.

Right Angled Pattern B864 to B867

Manufactured to the requirements of the British Meteorological Office for measuring earth temperatures at depths up to 300mm, the solid mercury-in-glass thermometer is formed with the bulb at right angles to the scale. The vertical limb containing the bulb, is immersed to the required depth and left permanently in position. The horizontal limb with the scale, subdivided every 0.5° and figured at 5° intervals, lies along the surface.

Earth Tubes B860 to B863

A seamless steel tube, black stove enamelled for protection, incorporates a brass pointed end for ease of sinking. A removable flange, set 150mm from the top end, controls the exact immersion depth and prevents the entry of standing water. A brass cap seals the tube and provides an anchorage for the chain, from which the thermometer hangs. Permanently set in the earth, tubes are available for depths from 300mm up to 3m.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	range	accuracy	division	dims. (mm)
B859	-10 to +45°C	± 0.2°C	0.5°C	360 x 20
Reference	immersion			
B860	300 mm			
B861	500 mm			
B862	1 metre			
B863	3 metres			
Reference	range	accuracy	division	Immersion
B864	-7 to +38°C	±0.2°C	0.5°C	50 mm
B865	-7 to +38°C	±0.2°C	0.5°C	100 mm
B866	-7 to +38°C	±0.2°C	0.5°C	200 mm
B867	-7 to +38°C	±0.2°C	0.5°C	300 mm

R W Munro Ltd. reserve the right to alter specifications of equipment at any time, in the interests of improving quality and performance

Earth Thermometers

Enclosed Scale Pattern B868 to B874

Meteorological Departments and Agrometeorological Stations in many countries employ this pattern to measure earth temperatures at various depths from the surface down to 1200mm. A mercury-in-glass type thermometer is mounted on to an opal scale. Supported by a thermometer bracket, the lower portion of the instrument is placed vertically in the earth, with the bulb at the required immersion depth. The scale, indelibly marked every 0.2° for accuracy, is presented at a 60° angle, so a reading is easily taken in situ without disturbing the thermometer. Insulated by an outer glass sheath, to which they are fused, the glass stem and scale are unaffected by the atmosphere and upper levels of earth.

Support Bracket B875

Constructed from steel with black stove enamelled finish, the support bracket is for supporting the enclosed scale pattern thermometer permanently in the earth at the required immersion depth. Two clips retain the thermometer, whilst leaving the scale in clear view.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	range	accuracy	division	immersion
B868	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	surface
B869	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	50 mm
B870	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	100 mm
B871	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	200 mm
B872	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	300 mm
B873	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	600 mm
B874	-10 to +55°C	±0.2°C	0.2°C	1220 mm

R W Munro Ltd. reserve the right to alter specifications of equipment at any time, in the interests of improving quality and performance

Rainfall

With Munro Daily Rain Gauges, the rain falls through a defined aperture and into an inner can. The contents are then measured once a day, or as required, by pouring into a measuring jar. The well-proven Dines Tilting Siphon Rain Gauge, with its unlimited collection capacity, produces a record of rainfall against time. It is frequently used in conjunction with a Daily Rain Gauge to provide a permanent record of the onset and cessation of rainfall together with variations in intensity.

In areas where water conservation is of vital importance, the rate of evaporation from lakes and reservoirs is essential information for agronomists, irrigation engineers, water engineers and others. The Hook Gauge Evaporimeter provides data, which can be converted to reliable figures on evaporation rates from large free water surfaces.

R001 Meteorological Office MK2 Splayed-Base Rain Gauge
The unit is made from stout copper sheet with soldered seams and the splayed base provides extra stability. It has a 127mm diameter brass rim and is supplied with an inner can, with pouring lip and a handle, an ordinary pattern glass measuring jar and a rainfall record book. A brown half-Winchester glass collecting bottle, can be supplied as an alternative to the measuring jar.

*Splayed-Base
Rain Gauge R001*

R003 Meteorological Office MK1A Cylindrical Rain Gauge
Construction of this general purpose Rain Gauge is also in copper sheet, with soldered seams and a 127mm diameter brass rim, but the design is cylindrical. It is supplied with accessories as for the splayed-base model.

*Cylindrical
Rain Gauge R003*

Tilting Siphon Rain Gauge - Tropical Model R208
This Rain Gauge is similar to the temperate model, but has a smaller collecting aperture and siphons after 25mm of rainfall, enabling it to be used in areas of intense rainfall. The instrument is finished in white paint and is fitted with a radiation shield to reduce evaporation from the cone.

R200 Tilting Siphon Rain Gauge - Temperate Model
The movement of a float in the collecting chamber causes a pen to mark a daily or weekly chart, which is viewed through the hinged front window. When 5mm of rain has fallen - represented on the chart by a linear distance of 50mm - the pen is at the top of the chart and the chamber tilts and empties. The pen then returns to the bottom of the chart, to start recording again. The Gauge is constructed from non-ferrous materials and supplied with a hand-wound clock. There is a choice of either fibre disposable pen, or nickel-silver pen and ink.

Tilting Siphon Rain Gauge R200

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	R001	R003
Dia. of aperture	127 mm	127 mm
Area of aperture	12668 mm ²	12668 mm ²
Rainfall capacity	140 mm	140 mm
Dims. (mm)	490(H) x 216(D)	480(H) x 140(D)
Weight	2.75 kg	2.10 kg
Reference	R200/R202	R208/R210
Recording period	daily/weekly	daily/weekly
Dia. of aperture	287.3 mm	128.5 mm
Area of aperture	64827 mm ²	12969 mm ²
Rainfall capacity	unlimited	unlimited
Siphoning occurs	every 5 mm	every 25 mm
Siphoning time	6-8 seconds	6-8 seconds
Dims. (mm)	840(H) x 502(D)	840(H) x 502(D)
Weight	36.0 kg	33.5 kg

R W Munro Ltd. reserve the right to alter specifications of equipment at any time, in the interests of improving quality and performance

Evaporation

This is performed with a cylindrical iron tank in which the water level is monitored, usually every 24 hours, by adjusting the height of a hook until its point just breaks the surface. The actual measurement is taken inside a brass still-well, open at the base and adjustable on three levelling screws, which provides a small area of water surface free from ripples. The brass hook gauge is supported on top of the still-well and has a micrometer screw for fine adjustment. The equipment is often used in conjunction with a floating Maximum/Minimum Thermometer and a cup counter anemometer which allows the evaporation measurement to be correlated with the surface temperature of the water and the wind-run over the tank.

*Hook Gauge B882
Still-Well B883*

*Floating Max/Min
Thermometer B884*

Galvanised Iron Tank B881

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference B881

Dimensions
Height 254 mm
Diameter 1220 mm
Weight 64 kg

Reference B883

Dimensions
Height 215 mm
PCD of levelling screws 250 mm
Weight 1.8 kg

Reference B882

Range 0 to 100 mm
Resolution 0.02 mm
Dimensions
Height 165 mm
Diameter 115 mm
Weight 340 g

Reference B884

Range -30°C to +70°C
Resolution 0.5°C
Accuracy ± 1°C
Dims. (mm) 340(H) x 140(W) x 60(D)
Weight 310 g

Solar Radiation

This easy-to-use instrument is in service all over the world, for accurately recording the duration of sunshine on a daily basis. It is made to a British Meteorological Office specification.

Campbell-Stokes Sunshine Recorder B831

Tropical for latitudes 0° to 45° N or S

Temperate for latitudes 45° to 65° N or S

In operation, a precision glass sphere is made to focus the sun's rays and burn a series of traces on a card, which is concentrically mounted with the sphere. At the end of the day the length of the complete trace, less any gaps for where the sun was obscured, provides a measurement of sunshine for that day. For maximum accuracy, the recorder must be mounted so that sunlight has unobstructed access to it at all seasons and for the greater part of the day. The roof of a building is often the chosen site. The sphere has to be adjusted in its mountings before operation, to suit the actual site latitude.

Made to a British Meteorological Office specification, the Campbell-Stokes Sunshine Recorder can be supplied with B.M.O. certificates for the glass sphere and frame.

Campbell-Stokes Record Cards

Record cards are marked with hourly intervals and made from a special board, on which even weak sunlight produces a clear trace. A Transparent Template is available to simplify measurement of the length of trace. The cards used must be appropriate to the season - long curved for summer, short curved for winter and straight for use near the equinoxes. The sets of cards are supplied to a British Meteorological Office pattern and provide one year's supply. All cards are suitable for use in either hemisphere.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	B831
Adjustment for latitude	0° to 45° North or South (Tropical) 45° to 65° North or South (Temperate)
Sphere dimension	102 mm diameter ± 1.3 mm
Sphere focal length	74.9 mm ± 0.25 mm
Overall dimensions	240 mm(H) x 190 mm(W) x 170 mm(D)
Weight	4.3kg

Barometric Pressure

These barometric instruments would normally be kept centrally at a laboratory or manned station. Based on a design of the British Meteorological Office, the Barograph operates on the aneroid principle and is widely used as an aid to short-term local forecasting and so is of value to agriculturists, irrigation engineers and others. Aneroid barometers are compact and lightweight, with no liquid component, as with mercury types. IM168 and IM169 instruments offer temperature compensation, so accuracy is not affected by high humidity or extremes of temperature.

Barograph B812

Mounted on a polished brass baseplate, the sensing unit is a seamless metal bellows partially exhausted of air and fitted with an internal spring device. Variations in the atmospheric pressure, cause the sensor unit to expand or contract. This movement is then magnified by a system of levers and translated into a vertical movement of the balanced pen arm which records the variations in a fine clear trace on a chart. The chart drum is driven by a spring-wound dustproof clock, with daily or weekly recordings available. The instrument is housed in a hardwood case with hinged cover and folding brass carrying handle. The front of the case and one end are clear glazed, for viewing atmospheric pressure and trend. Supplied with sufficient charts and ink for one year's operation.

Aneroid Barometer IM168

Designed for use under tropical or temperate conditions, this instrument has provision for temperature compensation, so that accuracy is not impaired by high humidity or extremes of temperature. The high quality movement minimises scale error and the effects of hysteresis and ensures the reading will not vary by more than 0.5mb after a change of 50mb. The scale calibrations are in millibars and inches and are viewed through the 110mm dial aperture. An adjustable pointer incorporated in the glass front, may be set as a reference to monitor trend. The instrument may be panel or wall-mounted.

Brasscase Barometer IM169

Made to a British Meteorological Office design, this Barometer is presented in a brass case with sturdy ring belt and finished in black enamel. It is supplied in a fully-lined Morocco-bound transit case. The dial, scaled through 360° and clearly subdivided every 1mb, is figured at 10mb intervals from 880 to 1070mb. A bimetallic compensation device eliminates the effects of high humidity and extremes of temperature, ensuring a high degree of accuracy throughout the range. An adjustable index incorporated in the glass front, can be set as a reference to monitor trend.

SPECIFICATIONS

Reference	B812	IM168	IM169
Range	950-1050 mb	900-1060 mb & 27-31.3" Hg	880-1070 mb
Accuracy	± 1 mb	± 0.5 mb	± 0.5 mb
Resolution	5 mb	1 mb & 0.01" Hg	1 mb
Dims. mm	205(H) x 320(W) x 165(D)	115 dia. x 64 mm (D)	136 dia. x 63 mm (D)
Weight	4 kg	0.75 kg	0.75 kg

MUNRO

Monitoring the world around us since 1864

R W Munro Limited

Gilbert House, 406 Roding Lane South, Woodford Green, Essex, IG8 8EY, UK.

International Tel: +44 20 8591 7000 Fax: +44 20 8551 4565

National Tel: 020 8591 7000 Fax: 020 8551 4565

Email: met@munro-group.co.uk

Web Site: <http://www.munro-group.co.uk>

The Meteorological Division of The Munro Group